

The Flexcrash Platform for Testing Autonomous Vehicles in Mixed-Traffic Scenarios

Alessio Gambi
alessio.gambi@ait.ac.at
Austrian Institute of Technology
Austria

Shreya Mathews
IMC University of Applied Sciences
Krems
Austria

Benedikt Steininger
IMC University of Applied Sciences
Krems
Austria

Mykhailo Poienko
IMC University of Applied Sciences
Krems
Austria

David Bobek
IMC University of Applied Sciences
Krems
Austria

Abstract

Autonomous vehicles (AV) leverage Artificial Intelligence to reduce accidents and improve fuel efficiency while sharing the roads with human drivers. Current AV prototypes have not yet reached these goals, highlighting the need for better development and testing methodologies. AV testing practices extensively rely on simulations, but existing AV tools focus on testing single AV instances or do not consider human drivers. Thus, they might generate many irrelevant mixed-traffic test scenarios. The Flexcrash platform addresses these issues by allowing the generation and simulation of mixed-traffic scenarios, thus enabling testers to identify realistic critical scenarios, traffic experts to create new datasets, and regulators to extend consumer testing benchmarks.

CCS Concepts

• **Software and its engineering** → **Software testing and debugging**; *Search-based software engineering*; • **General and reference** → Empirical studies.

Keywords

Scenario-based testing, human in the loop, multi-agent simulations

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1 Introduction

Autonomous vehicles (AV) are expected to improve our society by reducing pollution and increasing safety in transportation. However, we are not there yet, as current prototypes struggle to drive alongside humans, a situation known as *mixed traffic*, and have already caused several accidents (see, for example, the State of

California DMV collision report [18]). To make things worse, an increasing number of AVs developed by independent parties are expected to share the roads, which, in turn, raises the questions of whether those AVs will be able to drive together safely and whether the resulting traffic will show critical emergent behaviors [2].

Generating mixed-traffic critical scenarios, i.e., driving scenarios involving mixed traffic leading to collisions, is important for AV developers and testers, social scientists, regulators, traffic engineers, and consumer associations like NCAPs [12], to name a few. AV developers and testers can use such scenarios to test their AVs under realistic conditions that are difficult to observe in real life. Social scientists can use them to investigate interference between human drivers and automated vehicles, identify incompatibilities in their driving styles, and refine existing driving models. Finally, regulators, traffic engineers, and consumer associations can study how the combined action of multiple AVs impacts traffic and optimize the roads and regulations accordingly.

Despite their importance, mixed-traffic critical scenarios are currently underrepresented in existing scenario datasets. They are also not fully considered by existing simulation- and scenario-based AV testing approaches that either focus on testing single AV instances against predefined traffic (e.g., [7]) or do not consider human driving at all (e.g., [13]).

To alleviate this problem, in the context of the EU Flexcrash project,¹ we developed a novel open platform for testing AVs in mixed-traffic scenarios. The Flexcrash platform brings together independently developed AVs and human drivers by addressing the following main technical challenges: (i) integrating different AV technologies while protecting the Intellectual Properties of their developers; (ii) identifying a simulation paradigm suitable for both AVs and humans; (iii) defining a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that enables people to participate in the simulations; and, (iv) bolstering the platform's scalability. As we discuss more in detail in the remainder of this paper, to address privacy challenges, the Flexcrash platform enables remote participation of both AVs (via Open APIs) and humans (via the GUI); to address integration and scalability challenges, it adopts the reference layered architectural style, standard Web technologies, and an established driving scenario format (i.e., CommonRoad [1]); and, to address simulation issues, it implements driving simulations as strategic, turn-based games.

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¹<https://flexcrash-project.eu/>

The platform was recently released; therefore, we could only conduct a preliminary evaluation with the project partners involving instances of a single AV (see [21]). Our research agenda includes organizing user and empirical studies to evaluate the usability and scalability of the platform and the quality of the resulting mixed-traffic scenarios, integrating industrial-level AV, such as Apollo [4] and Autoware [3], and enabling the application of state-of-the-art approaches for critical scenario generation.

2 The Flexcrash Platform in a Nutshell

The Flexcrash platform allows studying the live interactions of humans and AVs in simulated mixed-traffic scenarios. Because humans and autonomous vehicles are very different beasts, the platform must adopt a simulation paradigm that is suitable for both. Likewise, the platform shall offer appropriate interfaces and APIs that allow AV and human drivers to understand the state of a simulation and actively contribute to it.

To increase the platform’s reach and attract more AV developers who wish to test their systems against other AVs and human drivers, the Flexcrash platform should consider aspects related to privacy and scalability. For instance, the platform shall not require AV developers to share any code for their prototype to participate in the simulations. Additionally, the platform must be able to deal with many concurrent simulations and drivers.

To address these challenges, we follow the example set by scalable Web applications and online multiplayer games that allow many players to cooperate and compete remotely. Therefore, to ease the integration of multiple AVs, the Flexcrash platform exposes a set of Open APIs. To allow human drivers’ participation, the platform implements an interactive Web GUI (see Figure 1).

The following sections describe the central ideas behind the platform design, i.e., implementing simulations as turn-based games, and its software architecture.

2.1 Turn-based Strategic Traffic Simulations

According to our design, human drivers and AVs that take part in mixed-traffic scenario simulations *remotely*; since we make no assumption about their network connectivity and reaction time, the platform must ensure that simulations work correctly despite possible network interruptions and delays in computing the driving actions. The solution implemented by the Flexcrash platform avoids real-time interactions and abstracts mixed-traffic driving simulations as *turn-based strategy games*.

In most turn-based games, players’ interaction is not continuous, and there are no stringent real-time constraints. On the contrary, the gameplay proceeds stepwise, i.e., in turns. We argue that this simulation paradigm eases the drivers’ remote participation, reduces the cognitive load on humans, and promotes engagement. Additionally, by simplifying the simulation execution, we both avoid the need for humans and AVs to be constantly attached to the platform and reduce the computational demand, hence improving the overall scalability of the systems.

In strategic games, players strive to achieve various –possibly conflicting– objectives by planning a strategy, usually without knowing what strategy the other players will adopt. We believe this is a natural fit for driving simulations, in which the objective is to

Figure 1: The Flexcrash Platform’s Software Architecture

drive the vehicles safely to a given target location while sharing the road with other traffic participants (see Figure 2) without necessarily having full knowledge of their intentions.

As the next section describes, during the execution of the simulation, the Flexcrash platform records each participant’s states and planned trajectories, checks for collisions, and consistently updates the scenarios’ state by enforcing a well-defined scenario life-cycle (more details in Section 3) at every turn.

2.2 The Platform’s Software Architecture

The Flexcrash platform follows established design styles and patterns typical of Web applications to achieve scalability, interoperability, and ease of use. As illustrated in Figure 1, it adopts a layered architectural style [19]. It exposes a set of Rest APIs and a GUI to enable the remote participation of AV and human drivers, respectively. Four main layers comprise the platform: The *Web GUI* displays users’ controls and captures users’ actions, including creating and visualizing simulated traffic scenarios and driving in them. The *Front End* validates the requests submitted by the AVs (via the Rest APIs) and the users (via the Web GUI) and dispatches them to the underlying layers. The *Scenario Management and Execution* contains the main business logic for user management, authentication and authorization, scenarios management execution, validation and consistency checking, and data export. The *Persistence* stores and retrieves data about users, drivers, and scenarios from the underlying relational database

2.3 Tool Availability

We aim for open research, reusability, and generalizability; thus, we released the Flexcrash platform as open-source software at: <https://github.com/Flexcrash/web-platform>. Videos illustrating this Flexcrash platform version in action are available at <https://youtu.be/NI4bvFHZU8> and <https://youtu.be/J3VwQL0RWUQ>.

Figure 2: The Flexcrash Platform’s Interactive Scenario Designer. Circles represent vehicles’ initial states (position and velocity), and squares represent target locations. Colors identify the drivers, which can either be users of the platform (Type = "Human Driver") or an autonomous driving agent (Type = "AV"). Roads’ direction is indicated with a triangle.

3 Using the Platform

We packaged the platform in docker containers² such that it can be easily built and automatically deployed via docker compose.³ Alternatively, it can be executed directly from the (Python) source, assuming all the dependencies are available.

Once the platform runs, users can access it via a browser or by directly issuing HTTP requests to its API endpoints. The following illustrates the platform’s usage in the former case.

The Flexcrash platform implements several use cases dealing with (i) user registration, management, and authentication; (ii) scenario generation, execution, visualization, and monitoring; (iii) and, data export. For the sake of brevity, we focus only on a subset of the implemented use cases.

Scenario Generation. Users create new mixed-traffic scenarios by selecting a map (called *Scenario Template*) and placing various vehicles on that. The interactive *Scenario Designer* (see Figure 2) allows users to add and remove vehicles, define designated drivers (Human Driver or AV), and specify driving tasks. A driving task consists of an initial vehicle position (circle), a goal area (square), and additional details, such as the initial speed in Km/h. Once a scenario is ready, the user submits it to the Flexcrash platform, which checks whether goal areas are reachable from the corresponding initial positions, vehicles are correctly placed on the road, and each user controls at most one vehicle in that scenario.

Scenario Execution and Monitoring. Once created, a mixed-traffic scenario enters a WAITING state until all the designated drivers join it. Next, the scenario becomes ACTIVE, and the simulation starts. Simulations end when their duration (i.e., the number of turns) is over, or the vehicles cannot move anymore because either they have reached their goal area or have crashed. At each turn, drivers use information about the current and past states of the vehicles to plan a driving trajectory, i.e., a sequence of “future” states where their vehicles will be. Next, drivers submit the planned driving trajectories to the Flexcrash platform that collects and validates them. Finally, when all the drivers have submitted valid driving trajectories, the Flexcrash platform computes the next state of the simulation and

marks the end of the turn. For doing so, the Flexcrash platform simulates the movement of each vehicle, updates their physical state, and checks whether any vehicle has reached its goal area or collided. Vehicles that complete their driving task are removed from the simulation, whereas vehicles involved in collisions are kept there but disabled, effectively becoming obstacles on the road. After each turn, the Flexcrash platform persistently stores the state of the scenario and all the vehicles therein. The platform ensures that past states are immutable but allows replanning. Therefore, drivers can adjust their planned strategies, for instance, when new observations about other vehicles become available. However, to maintain scenario consistency, users can only update “future” states (w.r.t. the current state of the simulation).

Scenario Visualization and Data Export. Scenarios that completed their execution are available for inspection to all platform users. Users can visualize each scenario state and retrieve information about each vehicle (e.g., position, current speed) or download all the data collected during a scenario execution (in the CommonRoad XML format [1]) to run automated data analysis.

Trajectory Sampling. Driving is achieved by submitting valid driving trajectories. The Flexcrash platform is agnostic of AV implementations and expects that each AV computes its driving trajectories locally before submitting them to the platform via API calls. However, computing valid driving trajectories is not trivial and requires fiddling with complex kinematics computations that not all human drivers might master. Consequently, requiring users to do so would strongly limit the Flexcrash platform’s usability and reach. Hence, we designed a novel, interactive GUI that implements a simplified approach for planning driving trajectories based on *mediated trajectory sampling* (see Figure 3). Thanks to this component, human drivers can interactively explore the space of valid trajectories (computed by the platform) from the current state of their vehicles by submitting high-level actions, such as “I want to move on the left/right” or “I want to accelerate/decelerate.” We argue that mediated trajectory sampling is intuitive, albeit less flexible, than directly planning the trajectories. Nevertheless, if a human driver manually computes planned states, s/he can submit the planned driving trajectory using the same API used by AVs.

²<https://www.docker.com/>

³<https://docs.docker.com/compose/>

Figure 3: Mediated Trajectory Sampling. Users can explore valid trajectories (black line) by submitting driving actions.

4 Related Work

Operational field tests are expensive, dangerous, and ineffective [14]; thus, testing AV in nominal and critical scenarios is done using simulations. Many driving simulators appeared in the past years, ranging from sensor simulation to holistic driving simulations [16]. The Flexcrash platform adopts the driving policy simulator CommonRoad [1]. The literature on scenario-based testing is vast, and many approaches exist [9]. Some approaches generate scenarios by replicating real-life situations, a practice known as scenario synthesis, by leveraging existing datasets of police reports [10, 11] and dash cam videos [5, 22]. As these studies showed, simulating safety-critical scenarios is paramount for testing AVs in situations that are difficult to observe in real life; however, these approaches suffer from low data accuracy and only replay observed human driving. Other approaches, instead, frame scenario generation as an optimization problem that they solve by employing metaheuristics and search algorithms. Relevant examples include the work by Klischat and Althoff [15] and Tian et al. [20] that generated critical scenarios using single-objective evolutionary algorithms and influential behavior patterns, and Cheng et al.’s BehAVExplor [7] that used multi-objective optimization to achieve scenarios diversity. These approaches generate many critical scenarios but focus on testing a single AV instance; hence, they neglect the importance of generating traffic scenarios involving multiple AVs. Only recently have some researchers acknowledged the importance of testing the interactions of multiple AVs as we do. For instance, Huai et al. proposed DoppelTest [13] that uses multi-objective optimization to generate critical scenarios involving instances of the same AV, while Maierhofer et al. [17] developed a platform, similar to the Flexcrash platform, for executing CommonRoad scenarios involving multiple AVs. Our platform is more generic than these works. It enables simulating scenarios that involve AVs provided by different parties and can also involve human drivers in the loop.

5 Discussion and Limitations

The Flexcrash platform follows the turn-based strategic game paradigm to simplify execution, align with existing planners, reduce the computational load, and improve scalability. However, doing so

makes strong assumptions about the completeness of the observable driving behavior. For instance, in critical situations, timing is essential, and drivers might implement erroneous maneuvers to react quickly to the upcoming danger of collision. Since the platform abstracts time, it might not capture such critical scenarios [8]. Nevertheless, we believe that the (abstract) scenarios that it generates are useful, either directly, e.g., as a means to improve motion planners under study, or indirectly, as a set of representative scenarios that can be *concretized* and exploited in other, more accurate, driving simulators.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

Simulating mixed-traffic scenarios is paramount for understanding possible future critical scenarios, optimizing the design of vehicle safety mechanisms, and developing high-quality and safe driving logic. Thanks to its platform, the EU Flexcrash project provides one fundamental tool for achieving these goals. In the current version, the Flexcrash platform implements the main functionalities to study live interactions of human drivers and autonomous vehicles in a prototypical way; therefore, it is suitable for running controller studies and small-scale experiments. Improving the robustness and scalability of the platform to conduct larger studies, e.g., throughout crowd-sourcing, is part of future work. Likewise, we plan to increase the platform simulation accuracy by integrating BeamNG.tech [6], a physically accurate and photorealistic car-racing game used in research (e.g., see [11]). Finally, we acknowledge that the Web GUI’s usability is sub-optimal; therefore, we plan to conduct user studies to identify possible future improvements and ways to increase user engagement. We believe that doing the Flexcrash platform could become a reference point in the AV testing landscape, enabling thorough testing of a wide range of AVs from early research prototypes to industrial-level AV stacks such as Baidu Apollo [4] and Autoware [3].

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References

- [1] Matthias Althoff, Markus Koschi, and Stefanie Manzing. 2017. CommonRoad: Composable benchmarks for motion planning on roads. In *IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, IV 2017, Los Angeles, CA, USA, June 11-14, 2017*. IEEE, 719–726. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IVS.2017.7995802>
- [2] Avishay Artsy. [n. d.]. San Francisco's robotaxi experiment is getting out of hand. <https://www.vox.com/technology/2023/8/19/23837648/self-driving-taxis-gm-cruise-alphabet-waymo>.
- [3] Autoware. [n. d.]. Autoware: Open-source software for urban autonomous driving. <https://github.com/CPFL/Autoware>.
- [4] Baidu. [n. d.]. Baidu apollo: An open autonomous driving platform. <https://github.com/ApolloAuto/apollo>.
- [5] Sai Krishna Bashetty, Heni Ben Amor, and Georgios Fainekos. 2020. Deep-CrashTest: Turning Dashcam Videos into Virtual Crash Tests for Automated Driving Systems. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, ICRA 2020, Paris, France, May 31 - August 31, 2020*. IEEE, 11353–11360. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA40945.2020.9197053>
- [6] BeamNG GmbH. [n. d.]. *BeamNG.tech*. <https://www.beamng.tech/>
- [7] Mingfei Cheng, Yuan Zhou, and Xiaofei Xie. 2023. BehAVExplor: Behavior Diversity Guided Testing for Autonomous Driving Systems. In *Proceedings of the 32nd ACM SIGSOFT International Symposium on Software Testing and Analysis, ISSTA 2023, Seattle, WA, USA, July 17-21, 2023*, René Just and Gordon Fraser (Eds.). ACM, 488–500. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3597926.3598072>
- [8] Florian Dandl, Klaus Bogenberger, and Hani S. Mahmassani. 2019. Autonomous Mobility-on-Demand Real-Time Gaming Framework. In *6th International Conference on Models and Technologies for Intelligent Transportation Systems, MT-ITS 2019, Cracow, Poland, June 5-7, 2019*. IEEE, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MTITS.2019.8883286>
- [9] Wenhao Ding, Chejian Xu, Mansur Arief, Haohong Lin, Bo Li, and Ding Zhao. 2023. A Survey on Safety-Critical Driving Scenario Generation - A Methodological Perspective. *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.* 24, 7 (2023), 6971–6988. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2023.3259322>
- [10] Alessio Gambi, Tri Huynh, and Gordon Fraser. 2019. Generating effective test cases for self-driving cars from police reports. In *Proceedings of the ACM Joint Meeting on European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering, ESEC/SIGSOFT FSE 2019, Tallinn, Estonia, August 26-30, 2019*, Marlon Dumas, Dietmar Pfahl, Sven Apel, and Alessandra Russo (Eds.). ACM, 257–267. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3338906.3338942>
- [11] Alessio Gambi, Vuong Nguyen, Jasim Ahmed, and Gordon Fraser. 2022. Generating Critical Driving Scenarios from Accident Sketches. In *IEEE International Conference On Artificial Intelligence Testing, AITest 2022, Newark, CA, USA, August 15-18, 2022*. IEEE, 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AITEST55621.2022.00022>
- [12] Global NCAP. [n. d.]. Global New Car Assessment Programme. <https://www.globalncap.org/>.
- [13] Yuqi Huai, Yuntianyi Chen, Sumaya Almanee, Tuan Ngo, Xiang Liao, Ziwen Wan, Qi Alfred Chen, and Joshua Garcia. 2023. Doppelgänger Test Generation for Revealing Bugs in Autonomous Driving Software. In *45th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Software Engineering, ICSE 2023, Melbourne, Australia, May 14-20, 2023*. IEEE, 2591–2603. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICSE48619.2023.00216>
- [14] Nidhi Kalra and Susan M. Paddock. 2016. Driving to safety: How many miles of driving would it take to demonstrate autonomous vehicle reliability? *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice* 94 (2016), 182–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2016.09.010>
- [15] Moritz Klischat and Matthias Althoff. 2019. Generating Critical Test Scenarios for Automated Vehicles with Evolutionary Algorithms. In *2019 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, IV 2019, Paris, France, June 9-12, 2019*. IEEE, 2352–2358. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IVS.2019.8814230>
- [16] Yueyuan Li, Wei Yuan, Songan Zhang, Weihao Yan, Qiyan Shen, Chunxiang Wang, and Ming Yang. 2024. Choose Your Simulator Wisely: A Review on Open-Source Simulators for Autonomous Driving. *IEEE Trans. Intell. Veh.* 9, 5 (2024), 4861–4876. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIV.2024.3374044>
- [17] Sebastian Maierhofer, Moritz Klischat, and Matthias Althoff. 2021. CommonRoad Scenario Designer: An Open-Source Toolbox for Map Conversion and Scenario Creation for Autonomous Vehicles. In *24th IEEE International Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference, ITSC 2021, Indianapolis, IN, USA, September 19-22, 2021*. IEEE, 3176–3182. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITSC48978.2021.9564885>
- [18] State of California Dept. of Motor Vehicles. [n. d.]. Autonomous Vehicle Collision Reports. <https://www.dmv.ca.gov/portal/vehicle-industry-services/autonomous-vehicles/autonomous-vehicle-collision-reports/>.
- [19] Richard N Taylor, Nenad Medvidovic, and Eric M Dashofy. 2009. *Software architecture: foundations, theory, and practice*. Wiley Publishing.
- [20] Haoxiang Tian, Guoquan Wu, Jiren Yan, Yan Jiang, Jun Wei, Wei Chen, Shuo Li, and Dan Ye. 2022. Generating Critical Test Scenarios for Autonomous Driving Systems via Influential Behavior Patterns. In *37th IEEE/ACM International Conference on Automated Software Engineering, ASE 2022, Rochester, MI, USA, October 10-14, 2022*. ACM, 46:1–46:12. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3551349.3560430>
- [21] Moritz Werling, Julius Ziegler, Sören Kammel, and Sebastian Thrun. 2010. Optimal trajectory generation for dynamic street scenarios in a Frenét Frame. In *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, ICRA 2010, Anchorage, Alaska, USA, 3-7 May 2010*. IEEE, 987–993. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ROBOT.2010.5509799>
- [22] Xinxin Zhang, Fei Li, and Xiangbin Wu. 2020. CSG: Critical Scenario Generation from Real Traffic Accidents. In *IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, IV 2020, Las Vegas, NV, USA, October 19 - November 13, 2020*. IEEE, 1330–1336. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IV47402.2020.9304609>

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